

Recommendation 20:

Using 'Personalization' to meet the societal need 'Inclusive well-being and health'

Status quo:

With personalized healthcare and personalized medicine healthcare service professionals attempt to

- determine therapy and drug usage by genomic profiles
- use biological information and biomarkers to gauge the risk of disease in individuals
- provide best possible therapeutic verifiable outcome with minimal adverse effects

On the other hand, the rapid evolution of the mobile application market has become one of the most influential drivers of personalization of healthcare for consumers. The rapid growth in the use of health apps offers important trending and insights in order to consider how health systems may engage or leverage consumer's personalization of health services.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

According to the PERMED project the main technological challenges to implementing personalised medicine are integrating big data and ICT solutions and bringing innovation to the market. Further recommendations are:

- Develop new decision support tools
- Develop methods to better integrate and evaluate the information provided by genomic, epigenetic, transcriptomic, proteomic, metabolomic and micro-biome analyses.

Non-technical challenges:

According to the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the PERMED project the main non-technological challenges to implementing personalised medicine are:

- *developing awareness and empowerment*
- *integrating big data and ICT solutions*
- *translating basic research to clinical research and beyond*
- *bringing innovation to the market*
- *shaping sustainable healthcare*

Inclusive well-being and health:

This broad category pertains to the pursuit of well-being, provision of a primary health care services, realignment between work, personal and community life and a stable work-life balance across all age groups and gender. Some instances of this need include providing basic health care services and personalized services for disabled and physically impaired, child care, maintaining the quality of life (work-life balance, cultural and free time), and reducing the stark economic and social isolation of elderly people. 10 of our informants mentioned this as a priority need. Their comments and concerns embrace issues such as "more appropriate medical care", "improved access to primary health institutions", "social cohesion", and "lack of solidarity and rise of selflessness".

Personalization:

Personalization, sometimes also referred to as advanced, user-centric customization, consists of tailoring a service or a product to accommodate specific individuals, sometimes tied to groups or segments of individuals, taking in most of the cases also the context in mind as well. A wide variety of organizations use personalization to improve customer satisfaction, digital sales conversion, marketing results, branding, and improved website metrics as well as for advertising. Personalization is a key element in social media and recommender systems .

*In the public sector, personalization goes hand in hand with the provision of public services to citizens and businesses at the ultimate level of automation (Level #5 - Personalized Transaction) , where eGovernment systems are in a position to pre-fill fields of the service applications, as well as to recommend and suggest services which are of need to the applicant, based on various criteria and possible life events.**

*Wikipedia – Personalization, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Personalization>
Koussouris, S.; Tsitsanis, A.; Gionis, G.; Psarras, J. (2010). Designing Generic Municipal Services Process Models towards eGovernment Interoperability Infrastructures